

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

FORMATION OF DIGNITY AS AN EDUCATIONAL TASK: ONTOLOGICAL AND ANTHROPOLOGICAL DIMENSION

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Abstract

The article examines the educational problem of bring-up of dignity from the standpoint of both defining the concept itself and outlining the ways of fostering it in the educational space. Dignity as one of the value orientations of modern education was proposed in a number of recent educational documents during the reformation of the New Ukrainian School. However, the documents contain inconsistent and therefore somewhat contradictory definitions of dignity, which requires a philosophical and educational analysis of the mentioned concept as a component of the further axiological development of national education. Therefore, the purpose of the article is to search for integral approaches to the uncontroversial interpretation of the concept of "dignity" and the trajectories of its formation in the educational space of nowadays. Such a search led to the need to combine ontological (in absolute terms) and anthropological (in relative terms) analyzes of the concept of dignity itself, in the light of religious cultural heritage, which over time was borrowed by secular forms of understanding dignity, but without taking into account the highest possible levels of disclosure of this value, as a virtue. It is proposed to remove the contradictory interpretation of dignity in different dimensions due to the recognition of the dynamic absoluteness of dignity. The trajectories of nurturing dignity in the educational environment are outlined, based on the interconnected phenomena of a dignified life and the personal ability to live dignifiedly. The educational constructs of the formation of dignity have been defined in accordance with individual directions of its acquisition: ethical, mental, social and physical. It is noted that the formation of the dignity of a growing individual depends on many factors, the most significant of which are the development of self-respect, the desire for self-improvement, and participation in socially significant and worthy activities. The given interpretations of dignity and the ways of its acquisition allow us to extend the concept of "dignity" as a value from the level of theory to the sphere of personal life development in the field of education.

Keywords: dignity, value, personality, school, virtues, education reform.

The problem statement. In the context of the reformation of the New Ukrainian School (NUS), the first conceptual documents appeared in the field of value and worldview formation of personality (during the years of Ukraine's independence). The significance (or even the revolutionary nature) of these documents is that they are a comprehensive attempt to propose a systematic approach to education through the proposal of certain sets of worldview values. First of all, we are talking about two documents: the program "New Ukrainian School in Progress Towards Values" [7], the main developer of which is the Institute of Problems on Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine, and the presentation material "Value Orientations of the Modern Ukrainian School" [10], which is presented on website of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, but without introducing the authors of this material. Both documents offer several basic national values of modern education, which are mostly common to them. The appearance of these documents was welcomed by the educational environment. The proposed documents are capable of determining the value direction of the development of Ukrainian education for years and therefore require careful attention to the interpretation of the meaning of

the specified values and the methodology of their implementation in the educational process taking into consideration the fact that these documents are limited only to a conceptual vision of the need for the value and worldview development of the personality without delving into the specified issues. That is why, the Ukrainian scientific community began to pay close attention to the various values outlined in both documents, particularly to the concept of dignity, analyzing which disagreements exist regarding the essence and content of the meaning of this definition, and therefore require some discussion.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Various approaches and attempts to analyze the essence of this concept are explored in modern scientific literature. Comparative aspects of secular and religious ideas about human dignity are considered by T. Kovalchuk [4]. R. Lutsky tries to understand the mutual influence of the legal and religious approach to understanding the essence of human dignity [6]. T. Prodan analyzes the relationship between dignity and religious freedom in the context of the post-secular dialogue. [8]. N. Devyatko defines dignity as the basic value of modern education [3]. Y. Volkova reveals the meaning of the concept of "dignity" as the highest social value of a person, from which all other personal rights originate [2].

The cited studies show that there are quite different views on the essence and content of the concept of dignity, which lie in the plane of the relationship of other values, for example, the individual and the collective, freedom or duty, secular or religious worldview models. In the new educational documents, exactly these opposites come to the fore and need to be understood to find effective structures for nurturing dignity as one of the proclaimed valuable components of modern educational modernization.

The purpose of this article is to outline integral approaches to understanding the essence of personal dignity and ways of its formation in the educational sphere as a declared value of the NUS through consideration of the above-mentioned opposites.

Presentation of the main research material. The concept of “dignity” is enshrined in the Constitutions of many states, that is, in documents that usually record the most important and most valuable ideas. In particular, Article 3 of the Constitution of Ukraine defines human dignity as the highest social value [5]. Article 21 emphasizes that all people are free and equal in their dignity and rights. According to these articles, human dignity is an inherent value for each person, as well as the entire set of rights derived from this concept. Based on the Constitution of Ukraine, the dignity of the person can be interpreted as inviolable and sacred, but other quite significant documents such as the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union do not use the concept of the dignity of the person though recognizes the fundamental importance of the same rights. And, as we will see later, there are good reasons for that. These good reasons also influenced certain disagreements in the interpretation of dignity contained in both of the aforementioned documents on education.

The program “New Ukrainian School in Progress Towards Values” and the presentation material “Value Orientations of the Modern Ukrainian School” contain two key ideas for understanding human dignity. The first one is that “by the very fact of his birth, a person deserves society to recognize his individuality and his beliefs, which, in return, obliges him to treat respectfully the legitimate interests of others (people – author’s note) and society in general” [10, p.6]. That is, it proclaims the absolute basis of the dignity of each person – the unique human essence given from birth. But in the previous paragraph of the same document, it is stated that “dignity cannot be an inherited or innate character trait, it is a value that is developed and formed, in particular, due to certain controversial situations when the moral foundations of the individual are affected” [10, p.6]. That is, the dignity of a person is already considered, not as an absolute value, but as a relative one, because it is acquired, formed, first of all, in a plane directly proportional to ethical growth: the more morally perfect a person is, the more worthy he is. In the same relative format, dependent on ethical development, dignity is prescribed in the program “NUS in Progress to Values”, where it is defined as “an integral value (super value) that includes self-respect, self-esteem, self-control, self-improvement. Own dignity reflects the significance of each specific person as a

moral personality, and also determines a person’s conscious attitude towards himself and the attitude towards him from others and society in general” [7, p.14]. Then we find an emphasis on dignity as an absolute value: “Dignity also expresses the idea of the value of each person who has either realized himself or can realize himself in the future” [7, p.14].

The double interpretation of dignity remains in the section “Value Orientations of the Modern Ukrainian School” entitled “Risks of Incorrect Interpretation of Value”, where the recognition of dignity is interpreted, on the one hand, as an understanding of the fact of the uniqueness and inviolability of its rights (absolute dimension), and on the other, as the fact that “protecting one’s dignity sometimes involves standing up for the justice and dignity of the weak” (ethical-dependent dimension) [10, p.7].

The content of value concepts that are introduced/reloaded into education must be consistent with the previous cultural tradition, otherwise, there is a certain risk of their incorrect perception in the realm of educational space. As you know, the most stable core of any national culture is religion. The culture-forming importance of religion and its influence on secular understanding through established forms of traditional consciousness require consideration of the concept of dignity in terms of the relationship, first of all, of secular and religious ideas to resolve the above-mentioned contradictions in the interpretation of the proposed value. In addition, a deep dive into the previous cultural and religious tradition of the awareness of dignity can help to find the roots of its double interpretation and possible ways to solve the problem of duality.

The religious doctrine of man (we mean, first of all, Christian teaching as a culture-forming one on the territory of Ukraine) has the basis of the initial premise of the individual, universal, equal dignity of man for all. The story of the creation of man in the first chapter of the Book of Genesis (Old Testament) [1, p. 11-12] clearly describes all people as created in the “image” and “likeness” of God, giving each person inherent significance and dignity by the fact of their origin, belonging to God’s created human nature. However, religious philosophy quite clearly distinguishes between basic “God-given” dignity and its concrete embodiment in life. We find confirmation of this repeatedly in the Holy Scriptures, an example of which is the episode when the Israeli elders came to Jesus to ask for a Roman centurion, a good man. They asked Christ to visit the centurion’s house and heal his servant. Their main argument was that “the centurion is worthy”. And they began to list his merits: “he loves our people and built us a synagogue” (Luke 7:1-9) [1, p.975]. Therefore, in the religious plane, “dignity” appears, at first glance, to be a double concept. The aspect of understanding, closely related to morality, is a possible potential source of various rights. In this case, human dignity is transferred from an absolute value to some models of a “dignified life” and ceases to be an absolute and integral quality, it becomes something relative, something that can be lost if you follow an “unworthy” life. From this perspective, people are not equal in their dignity but can differ from each other according to their spiritual level

and moral state, depending on their way of life and behavior, respectively. The first aspect is considered ontological because human dignity comes from the fact of God's creation and God's plan for man. The image of God is the most important value of a human personality, but it is generally known in Christian teaching that it cannot be called "dignity" in its full disclosure. This image is something like a sketch that needs to be realized. This is the potential to become a real person. Since even the image of God could be distorted and corrupted by sin, acquiring the fullness of one's development remains extremely relevant.

As soon as a person begins to realize this potential and his true nature, the second component of the concept of "dignity" is added: a person becomes not only real but also godlike. In patristics, this process is known as theosis or deification. The understanding of theosis does not pay attention to the conditions of a decent life and prefers the theme of self-improvement. What we wrote about earlier in the article "Metamorphosis as a subject of philosophical and educational analysis" [9]. If we talk about "deification" as the realization of the divine potential in man, then we should avoid some kind of fatalism, if man could not have any opportunity to participate in the realization of his nature. The theories and statements about the possibility of crime or guilt in the philosophical secular sense or about sin in its theological terminological sense would not make sense.

So, at first glance, it seems that in the religious and cultural tradition, we also deal, at least, with two approaches to the issue of human dignity, which left the plane of religious discourse over time (and we see this in the proposed educational documents) and differ from each other in a certain way. On the one hand, we have an unchanging, but not static (because it needs to be fully disclosed) concept of dignity, based on the principles of human individuality, based on which all people are equally worthy, and on the other hand, a more dynamic model with collectivist and moral emphasis. To some extent, this leads to opposition between the principle of freedom and the principle of order or harmony and the question of which principle deserves more attention remains open. However, in the religious dimension, the non-static nature of dignity as an image of God, which needs its disclosure, removes the strict opposition of two approaches to the interpretation of dignity: the concept of theosis takes place in the plane of synergy between man and God, which usually requires certain moral efforts from man.

Is there a leveling of this opposition in the secular worldview? To begin with, we have nothing but empirical evidence to the contrary. After all, at least in cases of insult, humiliation, and betrayal, the idea of dignity immediately becomes a fact of life experience, and therefore, an understandable reality. But what can be known about the dignity of a person beyond the empiricalness of his feelings? Of course, every person has something that can be damaged by violence, repression, torture, or discrimination. Although this "something" is really hard to put into words. Therefore, despite all the "buts", the term "dignity" continues, for lack of a better option, to be used as a kind of crutch. But there are also

supporters of the fact that it is better to talk about the self-evidentness of the term, which is based on the mentioned negative experience of humiliation. This experience is perceived as independent of cultural or ideological contexts and thus becomes static, losing the context of the fullness of its disclosure. We see echoes of this interpretation in the proposed educational documents, where the concept of human dignity is a normative concept derived from two-sided attempts to describe the equally valuable and fragile basis of human nature.

However, two mutually contradictory approaches to the question of determining human dignity remain unresolved in secular considerations. However, both worldviews (religious and secular) can contain resources for mutual enrichment beyond superficial disputes over the right to be the best of alternatives. Here is a proposal for a possible reconciliation: if a person was created by God (religious worldview), and received life as a gift (secular worldview), then this means that no person can claim disrespectful treatment/lack of respect for the rights/failure to recognize the significance of another person, which can acquire its unfolding/improvement as a person. With this interpretation, the problem of the contradictory understanding of dignity as a value is removed, since relativization concerns only the dynamic aspects of its acquisition, and not the fundamental value itself.

The educational documents reviewed by us contain examples of when the value is actualized in the educational process and when it does not receive sufficient interpretation. None of them outlines proposals for revealing its potential in the educational field. Therefore, the next step is to determine the philosophical and educational means of personal acquisition of dignity as a fundamental value, which includes a typology of the understanding of dignity and factors affecting a dignified life.

Determining the typology of the dimensions of understanding dignity allows for developing the educational space by the directions of its acquisition and potential disclosure.

Firstly, let's pay attention to the already considered dimension which is moral dignity. This type of dignity is related to a person's internal moral attitude which is manifested in actions and behavior that correspond to ethical principles and norms. A morally worthy person behaves honestly, fairly, and responsibly, and adheres to these principles, regardless of the circumstances. "Worthy of respect" is usually a benevolent person. The potential for growth in the direction of moral dignity is endless.

Secondly, there is intellectual dignity. This type of dignity is related to a person's level of intellectual development and his ability to think and solve problems. A person with intellectual dignity has a wide worldview horizon, knows how to analyze information, distinguish between truth and error, resist manipulation, make informed decisions, and build his logic of thinking. This type of dignity directly depends on intellectual development, on the ability to learn throughout life. Potentially, intellectual dignity can be revealed as much as cognitive abilities operate in human life.

Thirdly, there is the dignity of a healthy lifestyle. This type of dignity is related to a person's physical condition and health. A person with physical dignity takes care of his health, eats properly, follows an active lifestyle, and observes moderate and useful physical activity. He feels comfortable in his body and is in good physical shape. The optimal physical condition allows a person to feel strong and energetic, and mental health allows a person to be balanced and able to cope with difficulties. Self-confidence and a sense of well-being are an integral part of mental health. The ability to set boundaries, pay attention to one's own emotional needs, learn relaxation and stress-resilience practices, and value and respect oneself is important for mental well-being. Regarding this type of dignity, we cannot talk about infinite growth, but attention to the acquisition of this dignity is able to ensure a higher and longer quality of life for a person.

Fourthly, there is social dignity. This kind of dignity is usually associated with social status and position in society. A person with social dignity has respect and recognition from other people, has a stable job, financial well-being, good relations with loved ones, and is generally successfully integrated into society. However, social dignity cannot be based primarily on the level of financial security and comfortable living conditions. Because in such a case, a "working person" (for example, a person of retirement age who does not have special material wealth, but enjoys comprehensive respect) will be deprived of social dignity, which is not only the possession of material but also spiritual and emotional well-being. Social dignity does not mean superiority over other people or the desire for power and control. Rather, it is related to respect for every person in society, regardless of age, origin, or level of achievement. The basis of such respect can be the interdependence of people in society. Indeed, a material situation with financial support allows a person to satisfy his basic (and not only) needs, provide himself with a decent standard of living, and feel independent and confident. However, social ties are no less important for social dignity: the quality of relationships with family, friends, and colleagues, neighbors is of great importance. Maintaining a social network and being able to interact with a variety of people contributes to a sense of social dignity and the realization of its potential.

The development of the potential for a decent life depends on many factors, in our opinion, the most relevant of them for the educational environment are:

1. Formation of self-esteem skills based on one's own needs and values. To live with dignity, a growing person must learn to respect himself and not neglect his own needs (not to be confused with whims), and also not allow others to neglect these needs, rights, and boundaries. There is nothing wrong with having boundaries in relationships with other people: a person should define those boundaries and learn to clearly articulate them while respecting other people's boundaries and not allowing them to violate his own. One should learn to say "no" in situations that do not correspond to personal values, without comparing oneself with others,

and without feeling unworthy of respect due to comparative "imperfection" and "failure".

2. Striving for self-improvement and development of one's skills and talents. Educational institutions should help in identifying them and finding opportunities for their implementation in the daily educational process. The more a person develops, the more confident about his capabilities he will be. One of the principles of life regarding self-improvement is the willingness to work and make efforts to achieve personal goals, as well as perseverance and purposefulness in achieving success, which is a guarantee for all kinds of dignity (moral, intellectual, physical, and social). Self-improvement also involves spiritual and moral development. A person with dignity always acts ethically, and decently, without violating laws and striving for the improvement of his inner world. At the same time, it should be understood that no one is perfect, and mistakes always accompany human life. Therefore, the ability to forgive oneself for one's own mistakes, correct them, and move on becomes relevant. Also, it is crucial to be able to forgive other people and free oneself from negative emotions and images for the sake of living with self-respect, which is a component of dignity.

3. Since the formation of any value must be effective, the opportunity to engage in social activities like volunteering, charity, etc., and strengthening social ties must be provided to form dignity. Interaction with other people and participation in social projects will help a growing personality to feel its significance and importance, contribute to dignified overtones of one's own life, as well as appreciation and respect for the dignity of other people and their contribution to social activities.

Conclusions. The value of human dignity acquired a certain dual interpretation in the introduced list of basic national values, which should influence the further axiological direction of the development of Ukrainian education. The roots of its dual and therefore somewhat contradictory interpretation of both absolute and relative value lie in the plane of religious and cultural worldview heritage, which later had an impact on secular forms of understanding dignity, but without taking into account the potential of revealing this value regarding personal improvement. Amid the removal of the indicated contradiction through the recognition of the dynamic absoluteness of dignity, philosophical and educational trajectories of the introduction of this value into the educational process were proposed as the development of the personal path of its formation, which is based on the interrelated factors of a dignified life and the personal ability to live with dignity. Understanding and comprehension of these factors and principles of a decent life will allow us to create harmonious and meaningful relationships with ourselves and the people around us, accept our own values, respect ourselves and others, take responsibility for our actions and deeds, and strive for the development of our personal potential.

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